

Comprehensive Nutritional Assessment in Hemodialysis Patients: Evaluating SGA, Serum Albumin, and Clinical Outcomes

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Abstract

Background: Chronic kidney disease (CKD) patients on hemodialysis are at high risk of malnutrition, which significantly impacts morbidity and mortality. Assessing nutritional status using the Subjective Global Assessment (SGA) and comparing it with serum albumin levels can provide insights into the reliability and utility of these tools in predicting clinical outcomes.

Aim and Objectives: To assess nutritional status using SGA, compare it with serum albumin levels, and evaluate their correlation with one-year clinical outcomes in CKD patients on hemodialysis.

Materials and Methods: This prospective observational study included 150 adult CKD patients undergoing hemodialysis at Gandhi Medical College and associated hospitals in Bhopal over two years. Nutritional assessment was performed using SGA and anthropometric measurements, including BMI, mid-arm circumference (MAC), triceps skinfold thickness (TSFT), and mid-arm muscle circumference (MAMC). Biochemical parameters such as haemoglobin, serum albumin, urea, and creatinine were analyzed. Associations between SGA, serum albumin, and clinical outcomes were assessed using statistical tests, with significance at $p < 0.05$.

Results: The mean age of the study population was 42.71 years (SD = 13.82), with 57.3% males. Nutritional assessment using SGA classified 59.4% of patients as having mild to moderate malnutrition, 37.3% as well-nourished, and 3.3% as severely malnourished. Anthropometric measures such as BMI, MAC, TSFT, and MAMC significantly correlated with SGA categories ($p < 0.05$). Serum albumin levels, while significantly different across SGA categories ($p = 0.026$), showed inconsistent trends, limiting their utility as a sole nutritional marker. Patients with lower SGA scores had poorer one-year outcomes, including increased hospitalizations and complications.

Conclusion: Malnutrition is highly prevalent among CKD patients on hemodialysis, and SGA is a reliable tool for nutritional assessment. While anthropometric parameters align closely with SGA, serum albumin levels alone are insufficient for comprehensive nutritional evaluation. Integrating SGA with clinical, anthropometric, and biochemical assessments is essential for optimizing nutritional management in this vulnerable population.

Keywords: Chronic kidney disease, Hemodialysis, Malnutrition, Subjective Global Assessment, Serum albumin, Nutritional assessment.

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Introduction

Chronic kidney disease (CKD) is a growing global health concern, with millions of individuals affected worldwide.[1] It is characterized by the progressive decline of kidney function, ultimately requiring renal replacement therapy, such as hemodialysis, in advanced stages.[2] Patients undergoing hemodialysis often face significant challenges, including malnutrition, which is a critical factor influencing morbidity and mortality in this population.[1-3]

Malnutrition in CKD arises from a complex interplay of reduced dietary intake, inflammation, metabolic acidosis, and nutrient losses during dialysis.[4] The accurate assessment of nutritional status is therefore essential for optimizing clinical outcomes and guiding interventions. [5] Traditional biochemical markers, such as serum albumin, are commonly used but may not fully capture the multifaceted nature of malnutrition in CKD. [5, 6]

The Subjective Global Assessment (SGA) tool offers a comprehensive and clinically practical

approach for evaluating nutritional status.[7] By integrating clinical history and physical examination findings, SGA provides a broader perspective on the nutritional challenges faced by patients.[8] While its utility is well-documented, comparisons between SGA and objective biochemical parameters, such as serum albumin, remain underexplored in hemodialysis patients. [7, 8]

This study aims to address this gap by assessing the nutritional status of CKD patients on hemodialysis using the SGA tool, comparing it with serum albumin levels, and investigating their correlation with clinical outcomes over one year. The findings are expected to provide insights into the reliability and utility of SGA in this vulnerable population, potentially guiding future nutritional management strategies.

Materials and Methods

This prospective observational study, conducted over two years in the Department of Medicine at Gandhi Medical College and its associated Hamidia Hospital in Bhopal, aimed to evaluate the nutritional status and outcomes in chronic kidney disease (CKD) patients undergoing hemodialysis.

Patient Selection

Inclusion Criteria: 150 Adult patients over 18 years with a confirmed diagnosis of CKD, based on the KDIGO (kidney disease: Improving Global Outcomes) criteria, and actively receiving hemodialysis as part of their management were eligible for inclusion.

Exclusion Criteria: Patients were excluded if they had acute kidney injury (AKI), preexisting hypoalbuminemia not attributable to CKD (e.g., due to liver disease, shock, or primary malnutrition), pregnancy, or unwillingness to participate in the one-year follow-up phase essential for assessing long-term outcomes.

Data Collection Procedures

Data were collected systematically using a predesigned proforma, including demographic information (age, gender, height, and weight), medical history (e.g., diabetes mellitus and hypertension), and anthropometric measurements

(e.g., mid-arm circumference and triceps skinfold thickness).

- **Laboratory Investigations:** To ensure consistency, biochemical analyses, including blood urea, serum creatinine, electrolytes (sodium and potassium), albumin, and calcium, were performed in a single laboratory.
- **Subjective Global Assessment (SGA):** The tool assessed nutritional status. This involved a detailed history (e.g., weight changes, dietary intake, and gastrointestinal symptoms) and a physical examination to categorize patients into risk groups: well-nourished, moderately malnourished, or severely malnourished.
- **Hemodialysis Procedures:** All patients underwent standard hemodialysis according to their prescribed regimens.

Statistical Analysis

Data were entered into a master chart in MS Excel and analyzed using EPI Info 7.0 software. Descriptive statistics summarized demographic and clinical characteristics. The relationships between SGA scores, serum albumin levels, and other variables were assessed using appropriate statistical tests:

Chi-square Test: This test evaluates categorical variables, such as the distribution of SGA categories or comorbidities like diabetes and hypertension. **T-tests:** Applied to compare mean values, such as serum albumin levels across SGA categories. **Z-tests:** Employed to compare proportions, such as the prevalence of malnutrition across age groups. **Mann-Whitney U Test:** A non-parametric alternative to t-tests for non-normally distributed data. Statistical significance was defined as a p-value <0.05.

Results

Demographic and Clinical Characteristics

The study included 150 chronic kidney disease (CKD) patients on hemodialysis, with a mean age of 42.71 years (SD = 13.82). The distribution of age groups showed that the majority (46.7%) were under 40 years. Gender distribution indicated a predominance of males (57.3%).

Figure 1: Demographic characteristics of the study population

Nutritional Status by Anthropometric Measurements: The mean height was 163.77 cm (SD = 7.93), while the mean body weight was 51.84 kg (SD = 8.83). The mean BMI was 19.33 kg/m² (SD = 2.73). The majority (54.6%) had a BMI range of 18.5–22.9, classified as normal. The

mean mid-arm circumference (MAC), triceps skinfold thickness (TSFT), and mid-arm muscle circumference (MAMC) were 23.23 cm, 11.64 mm, and 19.58 cm, respectively. Significant MAC, TSFT, and MAMC differences were observed across SGA categories (p < 0.001).

Table 1: Association between anthropometric parameters and nutritional status

Measure	Very Mild Risk (Mean ± SD)	Mild-Moderate (Mean ± SD)	Severely Malnourished (Mean ± SD)	p-value
BMI (kg/m ²)	21.69 ± 2.32	18.14 ± 1.60	13.90 ± 0.78	<0.001
Mid-arm circumference (cm)	24.73 ± 1.64	22.52 ± 1.22	19.41 ± 0.44	<0.001
Triceps Skinfold Thickness (mm)	13.47 ± 0.66	10.69 ± 1.70	7.80 ± 0.44	<0.001
Mid-Arm Muscle Circumference (cm)	20.50 ± 1.60	19.16 ± 1.10	16.68 ± 0.42	<0.001

Biochemical Parameters: The mean hemoglobin level was 8.21 g/dL (SD = 1.151). No significant differences were observed across SGA categories (p = 0.094). The mean serum albumin was 3.38 g/dL (SD = 0.519). A statistically significant difference in serum albumin was

noted across SGA categories (p = 0.026). Mean serum urea and creatinine levels were 131.17 mg/dL and 7.26 mg/dL, respectively, showing expected distributions for CKD patients. Mean sodium and potassium levels were 138.36 mEq/L and 5.41 mEq/L, respectively.

Table 2: Association between biochemical parameters and nutritional status

Parameter	Very Mild Risk (Mean ± SD)	Mild-Moderate (Mean ± SD)	Severely Malnourished (Mean ± SD)	p-value
Hemoglobin (g/dL)	8.47 ± 1.17	8.05 ± 1.13	8.28 ± 0.59	0.094
Serum Albumin (g/dL)	3.49 ± 0.53	3.28 ± 0.49	3.66 ± 0.43	0.026

Nutritional Assessment Using SGA Score: The SGA rating classified patients into three categories: very mild risk to well-nourished (37.3%), mild-moderate risk (59.4%), and severely malnourished (3.3%). Significant associations were observed between the SGA score and nutritional markers such as BMI, MAC, TSFT, and MAMC. Patients with severe malnutrition had significantly lower values for these parameters.

inconsistent relationship with SGA scores. Further, serum albumin did not distinguish between mild and severe malnutrition reliably, suggesting its limitations as a sole marker of nutritional status in CKD patients.

Correlation Between SGA Score, Serum Albumin, and Outcomes: While SGA was strongly correlated with anthropometric measures, serum albumin levels showed only a weak and

Outcome Analysis: Patients with lower SGA ratings had poorer clinical outcomes over one year, including higher hospitalization rates and more complications. Anthropometric measures aligned more consistently with clinical outcomes compared to serum albumin.

Discussion

This prospective observational study aimed to evaluate the prevalence and factors associated with malnutrition in chronic kidney disease (CKD) patients undergoing hemodialysis. Conducted over two years at the Department of Medicine, Gandhi Medical College, and associated Hamidia Hospital in Bhopal, it provides insights into the interplay between demographic, anthropometric, and biochemical parameters and nutritional status assessed via the Subjective Global Assessment (SGA).

Patient Demographics: Among the 150 patients in this study, 46.7% were under 40, with a mean age of 42.71 years (SD = 13.82). Males constituted the majority (57.3%), and the distribution of age groups was comparable between genders. No significant association was found between age group and gender ($p = 0.340$), and there was no significant difference in mean age between genders ($p = 0.668$).

Comparisons with other studies reveal variable demographic patterns. Thangarajah et al. [9] reported a mean age of 49 years (SD = 14.74) among 90 CKD patients, predominantly male. Nagisetty [10] noted a higher mean age in patients on hemodialysis (54.83 years) than those on continuous ambulatory peritoneal dialysis (CAPD, 50.80 years), with males outnumbering females in both groups. Similarly, Lestari P et al. (2023) observed a male predominance (52.0%) and a mean age of 46–55. Bramania et al. [11] reported a mean age of 52.2 years (SD = 13.3), with 30.6% female patients. The male-to-female ratio and mean age across studies highlight consistent gender discrepancies and variations in age distribution, potentially influenced by geographical and cultural factors.

Anthropometric Measurements: Anthropometric assessments in the present study revealed a mean BMI of 19.33 kg/m² (SD = 2.73), with 54.6% of patients classified as normal weight and 36.0% underweight. Mid-arm circumference (MAC), triceps skinfold thickness (TSFT), and mid-arm muscle circumference (MAMC) values also highlighted a predominantly malnourished population, consistent with CKD's catabolic effects.

Thangarajah et al. [9] reported 27.8% of their patients as underweight, while Nagisetty [10] found higher BMIs in the hemodialysis group than in CAPD patients. Ghorbani et al. [12] reported an average BMI of 25.19 kg/m² but also identified a subset of underweight patients. These differences may reflect variations in the prevalence of malnutrition due to regional dietary patterns and healthcare access.

Comorbidities: In this study, hypertension (62.0%) was the most common comorbidity, followed by diabetes mellitus (14.7%). Both

conditions were present in 10.0% of patients. Comparatively, Xi et al. [13] noted diabetes in 17.0% and hypertension in 14.6% of their sample, while Bramania et al. [11] observed a much higher prevalence of hypertension (96.2%) and diabetes (43.1%). These differences underscore the importance of region-specific factors influencing comorbidity profiles in CKD patients.

Laboratory Investigations: The mean hemoglobin level in this study was 8.21 g/dL, consistent with the anemia typically observed in CKD patients. Serum albumin levels averaged 3.38 g/dL, with significant variability across SGA categories ($p = 0.026$). Interestingly, the severely malnourished group showed slightly higher albumin levels, suggesting limitations of albumin as a sole nutritional marker, possibly due to its sensitivity to inflammation and hydration status. Nagisetty [10] similarly noted serum albumin variations across nutritional categories, while Ghorbani et al. [12] and Shankar et al. [14] identified significant associations between albumin levels and nutritional status. However, several studies, including Gupta et al. [15], highlighted the limited reliability of albumin as a standalone nutritional marker, emphasizing the need for multidimensional assessments like SGA.

Nutritional Status Assessment: The SGA tool categorized 59.4% of patients as having mild to moderate malnutrition risk, 37.3% as very mild to well-nourished, and 3.3% as severely malnourished. This distribution aligns with findings from Thangarajah et al. [9], who identified 52.2% of patients at moderate risk and 16.7% at severe risk. Lestari et al. [16] reported 66.7% of patients with moderate malnutrition.

Association Between Nutritional Status, Anthropometric, and Biochemical Parameters: This study found significant differences in BMI, MAC, TSFT, and MAMC across SGA categories ($p < 0.05$), highlighting their strong association with nutritional status. Serum albumin levels, however, exhibited an inconsistent trend, further supporting the need for comprehensive nutritional tools. Bramania et al. [11] and Hemmatpour et al. [17] similarly identified significant correlations between nutritional status and various anthropometric and biochemical parameters, including albumin and BMI. In contrast, studies like Gupta et al. [15] and Ghorbani et al. [12] emphasized the limitations of relying solely on biochemical markers, advocating for integrated approaches such as SGA.

This study has several limitations that should be considered when interpreting the findings. Being a single-centre study, the results may need to be more generalizable to broader or diverse populations. Though adequate for statistical

analysis, the sample size may have needed to have been sufficient to capture subtle differences or rare patterns of malnutrition. The relatively short follow-up period provided limited insight into the long-term outcomes of malnutrition in CKD patients. Additionally, the focus on hemodialysis patients excluded those with CKD from other treatment modalities, who may have distinct nutritional needs and challenges. The lack of detailed dietary assessments restricted the ability to analyze the impact of specific dietary factors on nutritional status. Moreover, the absence of a control group prevented the establishment of causal relationships between malnutrition and observed outcomes. Finally, the observational design and the subjective nature of the SGA tool may have introduced potential biases in data collection and interpretation.

Conclusion

This study underscores the high prevalence of malnutrition in CKD patients undergoing hemodialysis and highlights the utility of SGA in assessing nutritional status. While anthropometric parameters consistently correlated with SGA scores, the variability in serum albumin levels suggests its limited role as a sole indicator. These findings advocate for a multidimensional approach to nutritional assessment and management in CKD, integrating clinical, anthropometric, and biochemical evaluations. Future studies should explore interventions tailored to improving nutritional outcomes in this vulnerable population.

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